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European forum and oBsErVatory for OPEN science in transport

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D6.2 Dissemination Strategy

Final

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Executive summary

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement”[1], T6.1 “Dissemination strategy and tools” and will set the foundations for the development and implementation of the succeeding Tasks within the WP 6.

The BE OPEN Dissemination Strategy document is the project’s guidance document for all dissemination, communication and exploitation activities. This document outlines an approach to reaching out and communicating to the target audience, by developing communication tools, defining a series of tailored actions, its timeline and persons responsible. It also sets quantified measures for monitoring progress and impact of the dissemination actions.

The strategic framework for communication and dissemination in BE OPEN is built on Chapter 2, with an analysis of the project goals and impact and consequent communication and dissemination objectives. This chapter also breaks down the target groups, defines the key messages and the different phases of the dissemination strategy. It concludes with two important grounding steps of any project dissemination strategy, the internal communication and the project identity.

The Chapter 3 presents the dissemination tools and materials and goes into further detail, looking at the plan and execution of the strategy including the timing of activities and responsibilities.

To ensure the high quality and impact of communication strategy execution, an overall monitoring and impact evaluation is drawn in Chapter 4 and will be implemented throughout the project.

This document will be updated throughout the project by the partners involved, in order to review the results and provide status and updates about the planned activities and expected impacts.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
KPI	Key performance indicator
TOPOS	Transport Observatory/fOrum for Promoting Open Science
TRB	Transportation Research Board
WP	Work Package

Partners' Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Partner/Third Parties' name
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
ARC	Athena Research and Innovation Center In Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies
BME	Budapest University of Technology and Economics
CDV	Transport Research Centre
CERTH-HIT	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Hellenic Institute of Transport
DLR	German Aerospace Center / Deutsches Zentrum für Luft - und Raumfahrt EV
EATEO	European Association of Aviation Training and Education Organizations
ECTRI	European Conference of Transport Research Institutes
EURNEX	EUropean rail Research Network of EXcellence
FEHRL	Forum Européen des Laboratoires Nationaux de Recherche Routière
FIT	FIT Consulting Srl
FTTE	The Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, University of Belgrade
GUT	Gdańsk University of Technology
HUMANIST	HUMANIST VCE
KT	Konnekt-able Technologies Ltd.
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
Osborne Clarke	Osborne Clarke Anwaltssozietat
SCIPEDIA	SCIPEDIA S.L.
Strathclyde University	Strathclyde University
TØI	Transportøkonomisk Institutt
UITP	Union Internationale des Transports Publics

VDI/VDE	VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH
VG TU	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University
WEGEMT	Foundation Wegemt - A European Association of Universities in Marine Technology and Related Sciences

1 INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement” [1], which aims to:

- Disseminate key project outputs to key actors and transport stakeholders;
- Implement and regularly update an appropriate online presence (web-site, social media, EOSC integration) and other relevant dissemination material to ensure continuous outreach of the project outcomes, as well as transfer of knowledge;
- Organise project key events and ensure cooperation with the most important international forums, as well as liaise with related projects and initiatives. Demonstrate the economic viability and lay the foundations for subsequent exploitation;
- Engage publishing companies and set up communication tools/actions;
- Supervise project results and key outcomes through an external Advisory Board, consisting of internationally renowned experts.

This deliverable under Task 6.1 Dissemination strategy and tools, will set the foundations for the development and implementation of the succeeding Tasks within the WP 6. It will establish a common strategic approach to communication, dissemination and collaboration in BE OPEN project, aligning and coordinating activities taking place at project and partner level.

The development of the overall dissemination strategy is led by ECTRI with support of the project partners, CERTH, TØI, VDI/VDE, ARC, Osborne Clarke, FEHRL, FIT, NTUA, DLR, EATEO, EURNEX, WEGEMT, UITP, HUMANIST and Konnekt-able and respective Third Parties.

Table 1: WP6 ‘Dissemination and Engagement’ Tasks and Responsibilities – Overview

Tasks	Duration	Lead Partner	Partners involved
6.1 Dissemination strategy and tools	M1-M18	ECTRI	CERTH, OC, FEHRL, DLR, EATEO, EURNEX, WEGEMT, HUMANIST, (CDV, BME)
6.2 Dissemination Activities and events	M4-M30	ECTRI	CERTH, TOI, ATHENA RC, OC, FEHRL, FIT, NTUA, DLR, EATEO, EURNEX, WEGEMT, UITP, HUMANIST, Konnekt-able, (CDV, BME)
6.3 Social media interfaces and research communities’ engagement	M3-M30	EURNEX	ECTRI (CDV, BME), CERTH, FEHRL, WEGEMT
6.4 Links to key events (e.g. TRA, TRB, WTC)	M8-M30	ECTRI	CERTH, ATHENA RC, FEHRL, EATEO, EURNEX, WEGEMT, HUMANIST, (CDV, BME)
6.5 Publishing houses engagement strategies	M8-M30	VDI/VDE	CERTH, ECTRI (CDV, BME)

The BE OPEN project will capitalize on the networking potential of each partner involved and multiply the outreach of the project’s dissemination and awareness raising activities. These communication and dissemination activities will run from month 1 to month 30 (full project duration).

2 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The aim of communication and dissemination in BE OPEN is to comprehensively disseminate the technical and scientific advancements developed in the project. The following sections highlight the project's main vision, goals and areas of impact and how communication and dissemination can help fulfil the objectives.

2.1 Project goals and impact

BE OPEN aims to create a common understanding on the practical impact of Open Science and to identify and put in place the mechanisms to make it a reality in transport research.

Achieving Open Access to publications, making their underlying data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and open where possible, and using open and collaborative processes and infrastructure via the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will be key factors in making transportation researchers share-reuse-reproduce science and in bringing such a critical sector closer to the society for enabling open innovation and citizen science.

Openness, transparency, fairness, reproducibility of science are key aspects around which BE OPEN will seek to establish the ground rules for the transport research communities, ultimately establishing a community of transport research organizations willing to work on the basis of a commonly agreed "Open Science Code of Conduct".

To this end, BE OPEN has brought on board key transport and open science related communities in a two-fold action plan: to engage them in a participatory approach fostering a dialogue on Open Science (what exists, what should be done, how it should be done) among relevant stakeholders in Europe and around the world, and develop a detailed roadmap for the implementation of sustainable open science modules which include key practices, infrastructures, policies and business models, all taking into account the specificities of the transport research domain, and the use and integration of existing-infrastructures and the emerging EOSC initiative.

2.2 Communication and dissemination objectives

The objective of the BE OPEN Dissemination Strategy is the identification and organization of the activities to be performed, in order to promote the project's results, achieve the widest dissemination of Open Science benefits and engage the targeted transport communities.

This strategy will seek commitment from all partners to contribute to its dissemination actions. It will describe in detail which stakeholders will be addressed by means of which tailored messages, which adapted communication tools and through which communication channels.

The key elements of the strategy include:

- the identification of target audiences;
- the specification of channels for connecting with audiences (events and media platforms);
- the cross-integration of dissemination output (print, electronic and face-to-face).

2.3 Target groups

To know more about who the communication and dissemination should target, stakeholders have been identified to establish roles, interests and communication needs.

Figure 1: Target group mapping (type of communication and general actions)

BE OPEN will conduct various dissemination activities to maximise the project impact, ranging from stakeholder workshops to one to one engagement with end users.

The targeted groups will be regularly informed about the BE OPEN project, will be invited to take part in the relevant events and to contribute to other tasks of the project (e.g. desk research, surveys, interviews). The main purpose is to build a strong project profile with the scientific community, the industry, policy makers, and users.

In addition, the establishment of the Advisory Board will provide important experts feedback to the BE OPEN project. The Advisory Board will comprise only experts outside the Consortium including

international and European authorities, industry, scientific and educational communities to assure that BE OPEN is progressing along the correct path.

More particularly to what concerns the transport sector, BE OPEN under the WP1 Focused Objectives of Key Actors, Task 1.1 Clustering of Key Actors, D1.1 Taxonomy of actors terminology and experimental tools [2] has firstly identified a preliminary list of stakeholders (i.e. research centres and Universities, researchers and students, private researchers, policy makers at regional, national or international level, transport networks, NGOs and community organizations, commercial transport and logistics industry players and citizens) and then it has narrowed it down to three categories of main actors of Open Science in transport that have to be involved through a more structured and focused approach. These are:

- Industry: the main European Technology Platforms, namely ERTRAC¹, ERRAC², WATERBORNE^{TP3}, ACARE⁴, ECTP⁵, ALICE⁶, ARTEMIS⁷, CEDR⁸;
- Research: the major influential research organisations, namely, ECTRI⁹, FEHRL¹⁰, FERSI¹¹, EURNEX¹², EATEO¹³, WEGEMT¹⁴, EARTO¹⁵, EARPA¹⁶
- Public authorities: the ERANET initiative and TRIMIS and CORDIS tools.

Therefore communication and dissemination actions towards these specific groups will be specially tailored.

2.4 Key messages, motto and phase approach

2.4.1 Key Messages

Dissemination includes permanent activities and provides key messages throughout the project. Therefore, the key messages will be evolved and adapted to each target group and platform. Furthermore, specific occasions and project milestones could be identified as particularly appropriate for outreach activities. These activities may involve organisation of events, presentation of key results, publications, innovation of use cases, etc.

¹ European Road Transport Research Advisory Council

² European Rail Research Advisory Council

³ European Research and Innovation Platform for Waterborne Industries

⁴ Advisory Council for Aeronautics Research in Europe

⁵ European construction technology platform

⁶ Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe

⁷ ARTEMIS Industry Association

⁸ Conference of European Directors of Roads

⁹ European Conference of Transport Research Institutes

¹⁰ Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories

¹¹ Forum of European Road Safety Research Institutes

¹² European rail Research Network of EXcellence

¹³ European Association of Aviation Training and Educational Organisations

¹⁴ European Association of Universities in Marine Technology

¹⁵ European Association of Research and Technology Organisations

¹⁶ European Automotive Research Partners Association

Target messages for each group of stakeholders have been defined (Table 2). The target messages will be used in discussion and communication with stakeholders. They will also be used among others as headlines e.g. at the beginning of some writing about the project or titles (of a paper, of any chapter etc.), at the end of the writing, or near/close to the project logo, or separately in parenthesis in a leaflet.

Table 2: Key messages according to target group

Group	Type of message	Key messages
Users	Technological dissemination/messages which engage the transport research community into the BE OPEN work	<i>BE OPEN promotes collaboration schemes among industry, research community and citizens in order to speed up the path from research to innovation.</i>
Producers and facilitators		<i>TOPOS will provide the tools to foster an evidence-based discussion and cross-fertilization of ideas amongst researchers in transport on the national, European and global scene.</i>
General public	Story-oriented dissemination/messages which inform the general public about BE OPEN work/open science/transport research	<i>BE OPEN promotes citizen's engagement in scientific process by working together for improved societal value via TOPOS</i>

2.4.2 Motto

The motto is meant to formally summarize the scope and vision, be informative and catch the interest or attention. BE OPEN's project motto "**Promote, regulate and standardise Open Science in Transport**", will be used across offline and online and interactive tools and channels (e.g. website, leaflet and roll up banner).

2.4.3 Acknowledgement of EU funding

As the project is funded by the European Union, dissemination, communication and publication materials must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding through the display of the EU flag and the following text referring to Horizon 2020[9]:

" This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824323"

A disclaimer will also be inserted stating:

“This document reflects only the views of the author(s). Neither the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) nor the European Commission is in any way responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

Further and detailed rules for acknowledgement of EU funding are available under [Annex I](#).

2.4.4 Phase approach

The strategy will be built around key Milestones and Deliverables which are particularly suitable for outreach and promotion towards the outside world as well as it will list relevant external events and media which could be used to further enhance the project’s dissemination and take-up activities. The dissemination strategy will be the project’s guidance document for all dissemination, communication and exploitation activities. The BE OPEN project will be able to capitalize on the networking potential of each partner involved and multiply the outreach of the project’s dissemination and awareness raising activities.

Figure 2: Dissemination phase approach

2.5 Internal communication

Strong internal communication and collaboration are paramount to achieve the defined strategic goals and for making processes as efficient as possible. To ensure proper execution of the dissemination plan and that the goals are met, partners are asked to:

- Be aware of the common goals for communication and dissemination and commit to them;
- Follow the internal procedures and use the project resources;
- Plan, share and coordinate activities proactively;
- Report to the WP 6 leader all dissemination actions undertaken;
- Make use of the BE OPEN private project management tool (Freedcamp), which will assist the management of tasks, project plans, milestones, communications and documents, etc.

2.5.1 Freedcamp

Freedcamp constitutes a private project management that facilitates information management within the consortium. This platform gives also the opportunity to project partners to work in parallel on project reports, saving them time and effort of merging separately prepared texts. [6][7]

2.5.2 Mailing lists

Three mailing lists with different groups of recipients will be created; one for the entire consortium, one for the Programme Coordination Group (WP and Task leaders) and one for the Advisory Board (AB). This separation will aim to facilitate the communication and interaction between the parties involved. Additional mailing lists may be created per WP or for any other communication need. All lists will be available at the Freedcamp.

2.5.3 Meetings

The Consortium will meet once per year for the optimal coordination and planning of the project activities. The meetings will be linked (when possible) to project events (e.g. workshops) or other major events (where most partners will be present) to avoid extra travelling costs. The date and venue of each meeting will be decided during the previous meeting, or when this is not feasible, through an online doodle poll initiated by the Coordinator, at least two months prior to the meeting. Agenda and minutes (following the relevant template) will be distributed to the partners by the Coordinator at least one month prior to the meeting, including the meeting structure and topics to be discussed. One week after the meeting the Coordinator should send the meeting minutes to all attendees. More information about the organization of the meetings is included in Deliverable 7.1 [6].

2.5.4 Teleconferences

Teleconferences will be held on regular basis, among (part of) the Programme Coordination Group for the proper monitoring of the project activities. Additional teleconferences can be organised when necessary to discuss specific issues at WP or Task level.

The organiser of each teleconference should agree on the date of the telco with the participants and send - at least two days in advance the date of the teleconference - the agenda and connection details to the participants in order to prepare for the telco. All teleconferences will be held through "Go to Meeting" or another similar platform.

2.6 Project identity: Logo

The project identity relates to the appearance and visibility of the project towards the external stakeholders.

The BE OPEN logo is at the heart of the project identity establishing a common and recognisable BE OPEN brand and visually translating the scope and vision of the project, as follows:

- The **transport research** is represented by the modes/means of transport
- The sphere stands for a lens representing the **transparency, openness, fairness and reproducibility of science**
- The dots and intersecting lines represent the **knowledge shared and developed through collaborative networks**

Figure 3: BE OPEN logo (primary version full color)

i. Logo usage guidelines

The BE OPEN logo will be used across all communication and dissemination materials. For this purpose, the primary logo version (Figure 3) should be used whenever possible, following the guidelines below:

Text font: EliotSans-Bold

Text color codes: HEX code : #052b35

RGB code (5, 43, 53)

CMYK code (91%, 19%, 0%, 79%)

Each element and its position in relation to each other have been carefully designed and must never be stretched, altered or distorted.

ii. Logo variations

The BE OPEN logo is also available in color (Fig.4, 5 and 6) and gray scale versions (fig.8 and 9), for use in white and dark backgrounds.

The logo versions in multiple high-resolution file types are available for partners use under Freedcamp management tool, together with the logo usage guidelines to assure consistency and quality use.

Figure 4. BE OPEN Color logo with text for dark background

Figure 5. BE OPEN Color logo without text for dark background

Figure 6. BE OPEN B&W logo with white text for dark background

Figure 7. BE OPEN Color logo without text

Figure 8. BE OPEN B&W logo dark text

Figure 9. BE OPEN B&W logo without text

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI and VDI/VDE are responsible for developing the project logo. All partners should use the project identity when communicating the project.	Month 3 (March 2019) Whole project duration

2.7 TOPOS

As an exploitation result of BE OPEN, the TOPOS (Transport Observatory/forum for Promoting Open Science) will have an identity of its own while keeping a strong link to the BE OPEN/mother-project. Therefore, before the establishment of TOPOS (planned for M26), the dissemination strategy will be reviewed in order to analyse the needs (logo, website, dissemination tools and materials) and define a short to medium term actions plan, for the promotion and outreach of TOPOS.

3 DISSEMINATION TOOLS and MATERIALS

All available tools and activities have been grouped according to their nature following three categories: **offline/non-electronic tools and channels**, **online and interactive tools and channels** and **face-to-face interactive tools and channels**.

3.1 Offline dissemination tools

3.1.1 Templates

Within the frame of BE OPEN, a PowerPoint (.ppt), meeting agenda (.doc), minutes (.doc) and Deliverable templates (.doc) will be developed in order to ensure visual uniformity in communicating. All templates complete and reinforce the identity of the project. All partners are required to use these templates when sending out documents or giving presentations.

These templates should be used as follows:

- The Agenda template should be used for all project meetings, conferences and workshop agendas.
- The Minutes template should be used for all project meetings
- The PowerPoint template should be used for all project related presentations, both internally (i.e. in project meetings) and externally in any other occasion (unless of course another specific template is required e.g. in conferences).
- The Deliverable template should be used for all project Deliverables both in terms of layout and structure.

Special attention will be given to the PowerPoint template, to ensure a common visual support for the lifetime of the project, as it will be used in many occasions for external communication. Partners are encouraged to share their concepts in a clear and simple way while they create their slides. They are also advised to adapt the content to the target audience.

The project templates are available under [Annex II](#) and under the Freedcamp project management tool.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI and CERTH-HIT are responsible for developing the project templates according to the BE OPEN graphic identity. All partners should use the project templates when communicating the project.	Month 3 (March 2019) Whole project duration

3.1.2 Project presentation

A presentation of the project’s aim, objective, expected impacts, key events and deliverables, will be prepared for the partners, to be used as a concise tool that depicts what are the key issues of BE OPEN. A PowerPoint file will be used for such purpose.

This will be available to all partners and shall be used in order to present the project on their own websites and social media interfaces, workshops, meetings, events, and any opportunities to promote the BE OPEN project.

This presentation will be updated during the project cycle and available under the Freedcamp project management tool.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI and CERTH-HIT are responsible for developing the project presentation. All partners should use the project presentation when disseminating the project.	Month 3 (March 2019) Whole project duration/ to be updated when relevant

3.1.3 Roll up banner, leaflet and poster

The roll up banner and leaflet will be tools for external communication, to be used for promoting the project at events and other occasions. They should both follow the project identity (logo, colors and typography) to make a coherent link between other communication tools. They will convey the project’s main objectives and planned impacts and will promote the website and social media platforms and references as a source for more information.

The content of the leaflet is presented in Deliverable 6.3[4].

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
<p>ECTRI is responsible for developing the project roll up banner and leaflet with an external provider.</p> <p>CERTH-HIT is responsible for the printing and distribution among the partners.</p> <p>Whenever possible and seemed appropriate, all partners should display the leaflet and distribute it when communicating the project.</p> <p>Whenever possible and seemed appropriate, partners should display the roll up banner when disseminating the project.</p>	<p>Month 6 (June 2019)</p> <p>Whole project duration</p>

The poster will present the project, its main achievements and best practices and be used for targeted dissemination activities, such as key external events and project events. This tool will be updated and adapted to each specific activity.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
<p>CERTH-HIT is responsible for developing the poster, with support of the relevant partners to what concerns the content.</p> <p>CERTH-HIT is responsible for the printing and distribution among the partners.</p>	<p>When relevant</p> <p>Whole project duration</p>

3.2 Online dissemination and interaction

3.2.1 Website

The project website is the central element of the project’s dissemination strategy. It is registered under <https://beopen-project.eu/> and designed to be the main tool to communicate and disseminate the knowledge produced by the project and make it available to the appropriate audiences. It presents the project concept and plans and will be continuously updated throughout the project duration to incorporate the outcomes and outputs of the project, as well as key information (policy developments, publications) relevant to the project.

The website is designed to be informative yet straightforward with clear language to ensure effective communication with diverse categories of stakeholders and external audience. The website further lowers user barriers by an easy-to-navigate menu, only a bit of text. Its design privileges dynamic content - images and diagrams, in addition to text. Furthermore, the responsive design approach will allow the website to dynamically adjust to the size of the screen on which it is displayed (computer, tablet, smartphones...). The website follows the project identity, in terms of logo, colors and typography in order to create a coherent link between all the planned communication tools.

Due to the widespread availability of platforms providing multilingual translation services, the website project does not contain an embedded translation function.

- News (e.g. announcements, events, publications,...) of interest to the project

3.2.2.1 Twitter

Twitter® is an online news and social networking site. What makes Twitter different from most other social media sites is that it has a strong emphasis on real-time information — events that are happening right now. It is a effective channel to spread project news but also to interact and to connect with a wide audience and is surely an important channel in this kind of project due to the frequent use of twitter in the sector. Twitter offers direct communication via comments and retweets, which will create an environment for conversations. Another tool is the Twitter lists where content can be more specific and more precise in targeting the foreseen audience.

A dedicated Twitter account has been created by ECTRI ([@OpenScTransport](https://twitter.com/OpenScTransport)) in June 2019 and will be used for a big scale bidirectional communication, with the users present on this social media, though converging to a more technical audience from transport researchers, transport related industry, policy makers, publishing houses and other open access stakeholders. This media will be crucial for the outreach and impact of vents, conferences or workshops to live broadcast the key discussions, messages and outcomes, as well as attracting new followers through real time information. By generating followers, a BE OPEN community will be developed, sharing the news in time and increasing interaction and knowledge exchange.

Twitter strategy

- Hashtags (#) are used to reach specific target groups and identify key concepts. Two to five hashtags per tweet is recommended.
- Use recognized and institutional handles in the tweets to maximise visibility and be recognized as part of the H2020 community.
- Make it visual with the use of pictures, videos, data visualizations in view to spark interest.
- Share posts and tag other Twitter accounts (up to 10), to build a relationship with our audience and make them aware of content that might interest them, in the hope that they will retweet it.
- Encourage conversations (by posing questions, thanking others that mentioned the project etc.)
- Leverage any existing social media presence, using existent partner's platforms, official institutions (EC and INEA) and other running projects, and motivate these parties to communicate information about BE OPEN.
- Create a BE OPEN Twitter list/ or sign up for already existing relevant lists. These lists can serve as channels for receiving news and provide pools of people/organizations who can share your posts, by tagging them or message them directly.
- Display the disclaimer as follows: "BE OPEN Project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation Programme. Any related tweets reflect only the views of the project consortium."

Table 3: Twitter identified hashtags and profile/account handles

Hashtags	Profile handles (non-exhaustive list)
#BEOPENproject #OpenScience #OpenScienceTransport #transportresearch #H2020Transport #investeu	@EU_H2020 @EUSciComm @inea_eu @CORDIS_EU @(BE OPEN partners)

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI is responsible for creating the BE OPEN Twitter account and keep it updated, with support of EURNEX. All partners are asked to follow the page, like, retweet and comment on posts, following the Twitter communication guidelines.	Month 6 (June 2019) Whole project duration/ When relevant

3.2.2.2 LinkedIn

As the largest professional networking site, LinkedIn® offers an excellent tool for connecting to the expert community working both in transport research and open science. BE OPEN has decided to create a LinkedIn group page aiming to build up an expert community of BE OPEN partners and related stakeholders in order to enhance collaboration and engagement. It will serve as a first interface in the perspective of the Forum on Open Science in Transport to be created in the frame of the project.

The BE OPEN LinkedIn group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12262083/>) has been launched in June 2019. It will be a place for dissemination of results, publications and promotion of events, but also a space for exchange of views and experiences on BE OPEN related topics.

Content will be managed by ECTRI and EURNEX. Partners are encouraged to:

- Follow the group and invite their contacts to follow.
- Provide input regarding news that should be promoted.
- Launch discussions and write their own contributions via their personal profiles.

BE OPEN LinkedIn members will also be able to exchange views and experiences on BE OPEN related topics while the stakeholders will be able to give their input in discussions around the main outcomes of the project.

LinkedIn strategy

- Define the rules for participation and provide orientation to all users; clear guidelines not only provide a level of comfort that enables members to confidently participate in discussion, they can also reduce the moderation load because they lead to fewer posts that fall out of the Group

scope; this set of rules will be published on Group Rules tab and in a discussion so members can provide feedback.

- Keep a regular presence with news about the project or other relevant activities, but also with those activities where the feedbacks from the community is highly valued.
- Use recognized and institutional handles in the posts to maximize visibility and be recognized as part of the H2020 community.
- Use the relevant hashtag(s) consistently throughout the overall project implementation.
- Make it visual with the use of pictures, videos and data visualizations in order to spark interest.
- Leverage any existing social media presence, using existent partner’s platforms, official institutions (EC and INEA) and other running projects, and get all these parties to communicate information about BE OPEN.
- Display a disclaimer as follows “The BE OPEN project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824323.”

Table 4: LinkedIn identified hashtags and profile/account handles

Hashtags	Profile handles (non-exhaustive list)
#BEOPENproject #OpenScience #OpenScienceTransport #transportresearch #H2020Transport #investeu	INEA European Commission Partners profiles

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI is responsible for creating the BE OPEN LinkedIn account and keep it updated. All partners are asked to join the group, like, share and comment on posts, invite following the LinkedIn communication guidelines.	Month 6 (June 2019) Whole project duration/ When relevant

3.2.2.3 Zenodo

Zenodo.org is a general-purpose open-access and open source repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts.

In this regard, BE OPEN will analyse Zenodo’s existing content in relation to transport and clarify the need for further creating and maintaining a living transport research community on that platform, for linking BE OPEN’s outputs to other deposited research within Horizon 2020 grants and finally for understanding how this tool can be linked to the TOPOS / Observatory to be created as output of the project.

The [BE OPEN ZENODO community](#) was launched on October 2019.

Zenodo strategy

- Create and curate a living transport-community during the BE OPEN project duration on Zenodo platform
- Explore how to maintain it after the project end period, in relation particularly to the TOPOS/Observatory to be created
- Contributions in every field of transport research are accepted
- Will be considered contributions Data Collections, Research Papers, Academic Publications, and any other piece of work which will have implications for the transport research.
- English is the preferred language for the contributions, but languages other than English are also welcomed.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
EURNEX is responsible for creating and curating the BE OPEN Zenodo account.	Month 6 (June 2019) Whole project duration/ When relevant

Further information in regards to the methodology for post scheduling applied to the regular postings and the specific campaign actions and key performances indicators (KPIs) used for measuring the impact of the social media strategy, are thoroughly described under D6.4 Social media [5].

3.2.3 Newsletter

An external newsletter will be regularly issued to present the latest results of the projects, success stories, related news from the partners, upcoming projects events, events where the project is disseminated, etc. The newsletter layout will be developed under Mailchimp with an external provider.

The newsletter will follow EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7][8], and it will be sent to all the subscribers who register through the website, e-mail or social media interfaces.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI is responsible for development of template, gather news and send newsletter to relevant mailing list. All partners are responsible for supporting development of newsletter content and for raising awareness/attracting subscribers.	From M9 Minimum 3 newsletters, more depending on the opportunities/ November 2019, October 2020, April 2021 (tentative dates)

3.2.4 Press releases

Press releases are pieces of content designed to inform or make announcements to the members of the media concerning upcoming events and their scope, as well as to present relevant outcomes and findings.

In this regard, BE OPEN will explore the most suitable media outlets at local, national and international level which can better convey the BE OPEN messages.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
Each consortium member is responsible for producing their own material based on the WP that they are involved in and disseminating to the appropriate media.	Up to 9 press releases, depending on the opportunities Whole project duration/ When relevant

3.2.5 Video

A video will be developed to visually bring the project message across and to illustrate the project's achievements. This tool will provide a highly scalable and cost-effective communication that can reach a wider audience and various stakeholders on the devices of their choice, in a simple and efficient manner. This video will be used for the final dissemination activities, with a strong focus on the project outcomes, notably the TOPOS, for further exploitation of results.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI is responsible for developing the video with an external provider. All partners are responsible for supporting development of video content and to promote this video to their contacts	Month 28 (April 2021)

3.2.6 Photo library

All photos from meetings, events and other related communication actions will be available under Freedcamp and a selection posted under the relevant page on the project website. Individuals that are clearly identifiable in these photos should have prior signed consent to the production and publication of photographs following EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
Partners are responsible to upload relevant photos from their own events on Freedcamp. ECTRI is responsible to upload the photos on the project websites	Whole project duration/ When relevant

3.2.7 Partners' own communications tools and platforms

Partners will use their own communication tools and platforms to raise awareness on the BE OPEN project, as mentioned in 3.1.2. A standard project presentation will be developed and shared among the consortium via Freedcamp to be displayed in their own websites.

Partners will also be asked throughout the project to promote the results, publications, workshops, meetings and other events of the project via their own communication tools and platforms such as, website, social media platforms, newsletters and/or magazines.

A full list of the Partners' websites, social media platforms and other communication tools is presented on [Annex IV](#).

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
All partners should display in their websites the BE OPEN project presentation, with a link to the BE OPEN website and social media All partners should promote the results, publications, workshops, meetings and other events of the project on their websites, social media platforms, newsletters and/or magazines.	Whole project duration/ When relevant

3.3 Face-to-face and interactive dissemination

3.3.1 Links with relevant stakeholders, other projects and initiatives

Partners having privileged access and/or cooperation agreements with relevant stakeholders, other projects and initiatives will explore these partnerships and propose concrete dissemination actions, to test ideas, share knowledge and best practices as well as to discuss future steps.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
ECTRI will disseminate information about the BE OPEN to TRB contacts (over 12000 transport research professionals), but also define joint actions with TRB, in the context of the ECTRI-TRB MoU action plan, which will support the BE OPEN project.	TRB annual meeting (every year, in January Washington DC) and other occasional events

Athena will establish links with OpenAIRE Advance and EOSC-hub projects, eInfraCentral and EOSCpilot.	OS Fair 2019 and EOSC events
UITP for multimodal sector	(tbd)
VDI/VDE, FEHRL will establish links with ERTRAC and road sector	(tbd)
EURNEX will establish links with ERRAC and rail sector	Participation in ERRAC Steering Committee meetings (several times each year) and ERRAC Plenaries Member of the TRA2020 Management Committee (27-30 April 2020)
UITP will establish links with Shift2Rail	(tbd)
DLR will establish links with ACARE, the Advisory Council for Aviation Research and innovation in Europe, which provides a network for strategic research in aeronautics and air transport so that aviation satisfies the needs of society and secures global leadership for Europe in this important sector. ACARE is essential in bringing together the right stakeholders to turn the air transport vision in Europe into reality.	Regular meetings of ACARE Workgroup 5 (WG5), which is responsible for the topics Infrastructures and Education
EATO will establish links with the air sector	(tbd)
WEGEMT will establish links with the maritime sector	(tbd)
TØI will establish links with Nordic research organisations as VTI, DTU and VTT.	(tbd)
FEHRL will establish links with road authorities through its members (one third of FEHRL members are National Road Administrations) FEHRL will disseminate BE OPEN results to ERTRAC, ECTP etc. The newly signed MoU between FEHRL and ECTP will facilitate this exchange of info about BE OPEN.	FEHRL General Assembly (twice a year) Annual meetings of ERTRAC and ECTP

These links will exploit and implemented mainly through face to face interaction and dissemination activities at the identified key external events and partners' and stakeholders' events.

3.3.2 Project Events

The projects events are a key piece for the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy of BE OPEN. Planned events targeting different stakeholders will aim at:

- Presenting BE OPEN results, conclusions and recommendations;

- Providing input for the project’s view and activities;
- Looking for validation of the content, endorsement of results and influence the project outcomes;
- Fostering exploitation and implementation of BE OPEN results;
- Discussing context specific issues concerning Open Science practices and implementation in the Transport field;
- Helping to define recommendations for the Code of Conduct on Open Science in Transport;
- Ensuring coherence and achieve harmonization of measures uptake among EU countries and in different modes of transport.

Three events are planned to be organised during the project life at determinant phases of the project development.

I. First workshop

The first workshop (planned for Month 10) will be organized in relation to the activities of WP1: Open Science framework and stakeholders views” and WP2: Mapping of existing Open Science sources in transport”.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
WP1 and WP2 partners are responsible for development of workshop content. ECTRI is responsible for logistical arrangements. All partners are requested to promote the event and are invited to join.	Month 10 (October 2019) 47 th European Transport Conference (ETC 2019), Dublin, Ireland

II. Second workshop

The second workshop (planned for Month 22) will be organized in relation to WP4: Code of Conduct on Open Science in Transport – Exchange with stakeholders to discuss the defined Code of Conduct and build up confidence for endorsement.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
WP4 partners are responsible for development of workshop content. All partners are requested to promote the event and invited to join.	Month 22 (October 2020) TRB 2020 (tbc) Month 16 (April 2020)

III. Final workshop

The third workshop (planned for Month 28) which is scheduled to 2 months before the end of BE OPEN project, will contribute to the setup and exchange with stakeholders on the TOPOS Forum.

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
<p>All partners are responsible for development of workshop content.</p> <p>All partners are requested to promote the event and invited to join.</p>	<p>Month 28 (April 2021)</p> <p>Brussels (tbc)</p>

3.3.3 Key external events

Participation at conferences and events related to open science and transport research will be a privileged mechanism to get in contact with external stakeholders and policy makers. The main objective will be to share and discuss activities concerning Open Science in Transport field. This task will consist more particularly of actively implementing the dissemination, exploitation and engagement activities that relate to the links and cooperation between the project's findings and results and several key actors.

Partners of the BE OPEN Consortium will actively pursue presence at existing conferences such as Transport Research Arena (TRA); World Transport Convention (WTC), TRB (Transportation Research Board), European Transport Conference (ETC) and others, like the Open Science Conference.

A non-exhaustive list, which will be updated throughout the project, is provided as [Appendix V](#).

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
<p>Relevant partners are responsible for development of programme and logistics.</p> <p>All partners are requested to promote the event and invited to join.</p>	<p>When relevant</p>

3.3.4 Partner's and stakeholders' events

Consortium partners' events and stakeholders' events will be also an important forum for BE OPEN project promotion.

Partners' will be asked to propose concrete disseminations actions, to test ideas, share knowledge and best practices as well as to discuss future steps in their own events and related stakeholders' one. The detailed list, which will be updated throughout the project, is provided as [Annex VI](#).

Role of Partners	Due Date/ Periodicity of the action
<p>Proponent partners are responsible for development of programme and logistics with support of other relevant partners. All partners are requested to promote the event and invited to join.</p>	<p>When relevant</p>

4 MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The main objective of monitoring and evaluation of the dissemination activities is to ensure a high-quality communication strategy execution. It is important that this assessment is carried out on a continuous basis to ensure:

- An effective impact assessment and update or redefinition of communication activities,
- Ensure the quality of the communication activities carried out.

ECTRI as dissemination leader oversees the overall monitoring, evaluation and reporting of the dissemination activities, according to the established objectives.

4.1 Communication activities & KPIs

In order to measure the impact of the activities and success of the dissemination strategy, the consortium set right from the start a series of quantified key performance indicators (KPIs) for monitoring progress and results.

The tables below present details of the planned communication activities and the linked key performance indicators (KPIs) for the different kind of activities.

Table 5: BE OPEN branding & communication material, channels/KPIs

Activities	KPIs
<p>Develop project logo, key messages, motto line, online & printed identity</p>	<p>1 project logo (various resolutions) 1 project motto in all key languages 2-5 hashtags to use when disseminating through social media 1 PPT template</p>
<p>Set up project communication channels</p>	<p>1 project web site Project social accounts: Twitter, LinkedIn, Flickr, YouTube or Vimeo channel for videos, Slideshare for PPTs</p>
<p>Develop communication guidelines & good practices for project dissemination activities</p>	<p>Document explaining communication strategy, how to use key messages, how to harmonise talking/presenting, how to use own social media for project dissemination</p>

	Guidelines for documenting & reporting project activities Statement templates for acknowledging EC funding
Produce printed project leaflet, banner and poster*	1,000 project leaflets in English (minimum) 3 project banners in English Project posters in English (depending on the needs)
Produce digital project leaflet, banner and poster*	1 digital project leaflet All posters will have an online version

* From the GA DoA, figures have been reviewed considering budget restraints and partners eventual needs in terms of communication tools

Table 6: Social media interfaces/KPIs

Activities	KPIs
Regular posting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 new Twitter follower/LinkedIn member per week on the 1st year of project • 1 retweet/shared post every 2 weeks on the 1st year of project
Campaigns	
1. Launch of website and social media (M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 Twitter followers/LinkedIn members by M12
2. 1st project event (M10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 Twitter posts during the event • 20 new Twitter followers/LinkedIn members by the week that follow the event • 10 retweet/shared post by the week that follow the event • 1-5 comments by the week that follow the event
3. 2nd project event (M22)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(To be defined in due time)</i>
4. TOPOS launch (M26)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(To be defined in due time)</i>
5. Final project event (M28)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(To be defined in due time)</i>

Table 7: Other actions/KPIs

Activities	KPIs
Campaigns for outreach to general press and media	(up to) 9 press releases on project stories & outcomes 2 interviews with local community members per year explaining open data approaches & their use for measuring the societal impact in simple language (to disseminate through various channels)
Promotion of targeted news items for scientists & experts via specialised channels	>10 news items per year on specialized project topics (through existing channels & newsletters)

Outreach of policy & decision makers informing about project activities, outcomes, successes, societal impact	1 briefing memo per year informing scientific communities 1 briefing memo per year informing funding agencies & donors (e.g. project officers, unit directors) 1 briefing memo for national/regional government officials (scientific advisors, officials in Ministries of Science & Technology, etc.)
---	--

Table 8: Scientific outreach actions/KPIs

Activities	KPIs
Publication of scientific papers in journals or conferences	> 4 publications to journals relevant to research governance and/or Computer Science and Information Science, and/or to social sciences > 2 publications to social science conferences
Organisation of special sessions or workshops in scientific conferences	1 special Dissemination workshop at the end of the project 1 special session or workshop per year
Preparation of articles in general science communication & publication outlets	3 articles per year at related blogs and websites

Table 9: Business outreach actions/KPIs

Activities	KPIs
Meetings with Business Units/Commercial Staff from commercial partners	At least 3 during the projects lifetime
Demonstrations of the BE OPEN recommendations and offering at funders and policy makers-dominated-events	At least at 2 related events during the projects lifetime

4.2 Monitoring and evaluation

To follow up and measure the impact of our activities, a dissemination reporting template is created under excel for monitoring dissemination actions progress and results. The form template is available as [Annex III](#).

This tool will be available at any moment through the project to be used by the consortium partners. Results will be periodically exported and analysed to feed the project periodic and final reporting.

The monitoring is a continuous process that will assess the overall WP6 activities and results, but also evaluate each individual activity and its impact on the project as a whole. It is most likely that the Dissemination Plan will be updated according to the results of such evaluations.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] BE OPEN Grant Agreement (824323 — H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020/H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA)
- [2] BE OPEN D1.1 Taxonomy of actors terminology and experimental tools (public)
- [3] BE OPEN D6.1 Project logo and website (public)
- [4] BE OPEN D6.3 Project leaflet
- [5] BE OPEN D6.4 Social media (public)
- [6] BE OPEN D7.1 Project Quality Handbook (confidential)
- [7] BEOPEN D7.2 Quality Ethics and Privacy Protection Manual (confidential)
- [8] BEOPEN D8.1 H-Requirement_No1 (confidential)
- [9] The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes -Guidelines for beneficiaries and other third parties (October 2012)
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/eu_emblem_rules.pdf

Annex I – Acknowledgement of funding

Acknowledgment of EU funding is mandatory in all communication and dissemination material within the framework of BE OPEN. The EU emblem (EU flag) must be displayed together with the programme.

Basic rules

- The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm.
- The name of the European Union shall always be spelled out in full.
- The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana. Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.
- The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not recommended in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way.
- The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.
- The colour of the font should be reflex blue (same blue colour as the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

Website & Social media account

- Same place on every page
- Ideally as part of the website frame which appears on all sections
- Landing or intro page (social media)

Brochure, information leaflet, factsheet, newsletter, poster

- Bottom right corner of publication
- Front or back cover
- On white background (unless placed on a large photo or illustration as on a poster)

Report/Deliverable & internal project publication

- Front cover

Power Point or other graphical presentation

- First or last slide of a presentation or in the footer of each slide

Video

- Intro or closing screenshot

BE OPEN Acknowledgment of EU funding logo and text

The BE OPEN project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824323

Annex II – Templates

Agenda

European forum and oBsEratory
for OPEN science in transport

[Title of the meeting/event etc]

[Date]

Venue:

Room:

Agenda

Time	Topic	Speaker

The BE OPEN project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824323

Minutes

European forum and oBsErvatory
for OPEN science in transport

[Title of the meeting/event etc]

[Date]

Venue:

Room:

Minutes

Participants per Organization

Name	Organization	Country	Mailing List

List of points discussed

[text]

Conclusion

[text]

Actions to be taken/ Next steps

Next actions	Who is responsible	When

Next meeting:

The BE OPEN project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824323

Deliverable

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824223. This document reflects only the views of the author(s). It does not represent the Commission's position and the European Commission is not responsible for any use for the results of the information therein.

European forum and oBsErvatory for OPEN science in transport

Project Acronym: BE OPEN
 Project Title: European forum and oBsErvatory for OPEN science in transport
 Project Number: 824223
 Topic: MG-4-2-2018 – Building Open Science platforms in transport: research
 Type of Action: Coordination and support action (CSA)

[DELIVERABLE TITLE]

[Version]

Deliverable Title:	
Work Package:	
Due Date:	
Submission Date:	
Start Date of Project:	
Duration of Project:	
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	
Version:	
Status:	
Author name(s):	
Reviewer(s):	
Nature:	<input type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O – Other
Dissemination level:	<input type="checkbox"/> PU – Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO – Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE – Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments

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Presentation (PowerPoint)

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation Programme
under Grant Agreement No 824323

**European forum and oBsErvatory
for OPEN science in transport**

Event name

Date, Place

Presentation title

Name of presenter, affiliation

Annex III – Dissemination actions reporting form

All Partners involved in WP 6 activities will be requested to complete the following form to describe any dissemination and communication activity undertaken directly related to BE OPEN.

Partner	<input type="radio"/> AIT <input type="radio"/> FEHRL <input type="radio"/> OC <input type="radio"/> ARC <input type="radio"/> FIT <input type="radio"/> SCIPEDIA <input type="radio"/> BME <input type="radio"/> FTTE <input type="radio"/> Strathclyde University <input type="radio"/> CDV <input type="radio"/> GUT <input type="radio"/> TØI <input type="radio"/> CERTH <input type="radio"/> HUMANIST <input type="radio"/> UITP <input type="radio"/> DLR <input type="radio"/> Konnekt-able <input type="radio"/> VDI/VDE <input type="radio"/> EATEO <input type="radio"/> LNEC <input type="radio"/> VGTU <input type="radio"/> ECTRI <input type="radio"/> NTUA <input type="radio"/> WEGEMT <input type="radio"/> EURNEX		
In cooperation with	<input type="radio"/> Other consortium partner(s). Which? ____ <input type="radio"/> External stakeholder(s). Which? ____ <input type="radio"/> European body(ies). Which? ____ <input type="radio"/> N/A		
Period	<input type="radio"/> M1-M6 <input type="radio"/> M7-M12 <input type="radio"/> M13-M18 <input type="radio"/> M19-M24 <input type="radio"/> M25-M30		
Place	<input type="radio"/> Belgium <input type="radio"/> Cyprus <input type="radio"/> Czech Republic <input type="radio"/> Germany <input type="radio"/> Greece	<input type="radio"/> Hungary <input type="radio"/> Ireland <input type="radio"/> Italy <input type="radio"/> Lithuania <input type="radio"/> Netherlands	<input type="radio"/> Norway <input type="radio"/> Poland <input type="radio"/> Portugal <input type="radio"/> Outside Europe <input type="radio"/> Other. Specify <input type="radio"/> N/A
Title and short description	<input type="radio"/>		
Activity	<input type="radio"/> Offline dissemination (display of leaflets, banner, face-to-face promotion) <input type="radio"/> Online dissemination (website, social media) <input type="radio"/> Publication (article, press release, scientific & peer reviewed publications) <input type="radio"/> Organisation/participation in a project event <input type="radio"/> Participation/dissemination in an external event (stand, poster, oral presentation) <input type="radio"/> Meeting with EU bodies/staff (Commission, Agencies, Committees, Parliament) <input type="radio"/> Meeting with other stakeholders <input type="radio"/> Other		
Used resources	<input type="radio"/> Website		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Social media <input type="radio"/> PowerPoint Presentation <input type="radio"/> Roll up banner <input type="radio"/> Leaflet <input type="radio"/> Poster <input type="radio"/> Video <input type="radio"/> Social media
Type of audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Scientific community (higher education, Research) <input type="radio"/> Industry <input type="radio"/> Policy Makers <input type="radio"/> Publishing houses <input type="radio"/> Media <input type="radio"/> General Public (civil society) <input type="radio"/> Other
Estimated number of persons reached	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> 1-10 <input type="radio"/> 11-50 <input type="radio"/> 51-200 <input type="radio"/> > 200
Feedbacks received	
Other information and comments	

Annex IV - Partners' websites, social media platforms and other communication tools

Partner		Partners' website and media platforms
1	CERTH-HIT	Website: https://imet.gr/index.php/en/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/hellenic-institute-of-transport-imet/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/HitCerth Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/HITCERTH/ Flickr: Newsletter: Magazine: Scientific journal: Other(s): https://www.instagram.com/hit.certh/
2	TØI	Website: www.toi.no LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/69190/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/TOIforsk Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/toiforsk/ Flickr: Newsletter: Magazine: https://samferdsel.toi.no/ Magazine: nordicroads.com/ Scientific journal: n/a Other(s):
3	ECTRI	Website: www.ectri.org LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/ectri-european-conference-of-transport-research-institutes/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/ECTRInews Facebook: n/a Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/people/80885158@N02/ Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: European Transport Research Review (https://etr.springeropen.com/) Online open access journal Other(s): n/a
3a	BME	Website: www.transportation.bme.hu LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/budapest-university-of-technology-and-economics/about/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/bme_en?lang=en Facebook: Flickr: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: Periodica Polytechnica Transportation Engineering (https://pp.bme.hu/tr) Other(s): - n/a
3b	CDV	Website: https://www.cdv.cz

Partner		Partners' website and media platforms
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/cdv---transport-research-centre Twitter: https://twitter.com/Dopravni_vyzkum Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/centrumdopravnihovyzkumu Flickr: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a
4	VDI/VDE	Website: www.vdivde-it.de LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/vdi-vde-innovation-technik-gmbh/?originalSubdomain=de Twitter: https://twitter.com/vdivde_it?lang=de Facebook: Flickr: Newsletter: Magazine: Scientific journal: Other(s): https://www.springer.com/de/book/9783319948959
5	ARC/ OpenAIRE	Website: https://www.openaire.eu/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3893548/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/openaire_eu Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/groups/openaire/ Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/groups/openaire/ Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): YouTube https://www.youtube.com/channel/UChFYqizc-S6asNjQSoWuwjw Slideshare : https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu
6	OC	Website: www.osborneclarke.com LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/osborne-clarke---germany Twitter: https://twitter.com/OsborneClarke Facebook: n/a Flickr: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a
7	FEHRL	Website: http://www.fehrl.org/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/fehrlcomms Twitter: https://twitter.com/fehrlcomms Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/fehrlcomms Flickr: Newsletter: http://www.fehrl.org/knowledge-transfer/dissemination/newsletter

Partner		Partners' website and media platforms
		Magazine: FEHRL Infrastructure Research Magazine (http://www.fehrl.org/knowledge-transfer/dissemination/publicationsandpresswork) Scientific journal: Other(s):
7a	AIT	Website: https://www.ait.ac.at/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/austrian-institute-of-technology/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/aittomorrow2day Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/AITtomorrow2day/ FlickrR: Newsletter: Magazine: Scientific journal: Other(s):
7b	LNEC	Website: www.lnec.pt LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/34909/admin/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/LNEC_PT Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/LNEC.PT/ FlickrR: NA Newsletter: "Tests and Metrology": http://www.lnec.pt/pt/investigacao/infraestruturas-de-investigacao/lnec-ensaios-e-metrologia/ "Water and Environment": http://www.lnec.pt/hidraulica-ambiente/pt/estudos/detalhes.php?tipo=1&id=328 Magazine: NA Scientific journal: NA Other(s): YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8ZgWrhujclVRKjGJ9O2fEQ
7c	VGTU	Website: https://www.vgtu.lt LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/vilnius-gediminas-technical-university/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/vgtu_university?lang=en Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/vgtuuniversity/ FlickrR: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: „Sapere aude“ Scientific journal: The Baltic Journal of Road and Bridge Engineering Other(s): n/a
8	FIT	Website: www.fitconsulting.it LinkedIn: https://it.linkedin.com/company/fit-consulting-srl Twitter: https://twitter.com/fit_moving_inno Facebook: n.a. FlickrR: n.a. Newsletter: n.a. Magazine: n.a. Scientific journal: n.a. Other(s): YouTube channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCycapSdUFhpGSYyeXqQtUWQ

Partner		Partners' website and media platforms
9	NTUA	Website: https://www.nrso.ntua.gr/ , http://www.transport.ntua.gr LinkedIn: https://gr.linkedin.com/in/geyannis Twitter: https://twitter.com/nrso_ntua_gr Facebook: n/a FlickrR: n/a Newsletter: https://www.nrso.ntua.gr/nrso-newsletters/ Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a
10	DLR	Website: https://www.dlr.de/ LinkedIn: https://de.linkedin.com/company/dlr Twitter: https://twitter.com/DLR_de Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/DLRde/ FlickrR: https://www.flickr.com/photos/dlr_de/ Newsletter: Magazine: https://www.dlr.de/dlr/desktopdefault.aspx/tabid-10625/year-all/ Scientific journal: Other(s): YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/DLRde Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/germanaerospacecenter/ Blog: https://www.dlr.de/blogs/alle-blogs.aspx
11	EATEO	Website: www.eateo.eu LinkedIn: n/a Twitter: n/a Facebook: n/a FlickrR: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a
12	EURNEX	Website: www.eurnex.eu LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurnex-e.v./ Twitter: https://twitter.com/eurnex Facebook: n/a FlickrR: n/a Newsletter: https://t.co/GdIYD2Lull Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: Other(s):
12a	FTTE	Website: www.sf.bg.ac.rs LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/faculty-of-transport-and-traffic-engineering/about/Twitter: Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/pages/Faculty-of-Transport-and-Traffic-Engineering/108358882528174

Partner		Partners' website and media platforms
		<p>FlickR: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a</p>
13	WEGEMT	<p>Website: http://www.wegemt.eu/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/wegemt/about/?viewAsMember=true Twitter: n/a Facebook: n/a FlickR: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a</p>
13a	GUT	<p>Website: https://pg.edu.pl/biblioteka-pg/main_page LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/biblioteka-politechniki-gdańskiej/ Twitter: @BibliotekaPG; @Bridgeofdata Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/BibliotekaPG/ FlickR: Newsletter: https://pg.edu.pl/biblioteka-pg/newsletter; https://biuletyn.pg.edu.pl/ Magazine: https://pg.edu.pl/pismo/numer-aktualny Scientific journal: Other(s): Instagram: bpg_gut</p>
13b	Strathclyde University	<p>Website: https://www.strath.ac.uk/engineering/navalarchitectureoceanmarineengineering/ https://www.strath.ac.uk/research/maritimesafetyresearchcentre/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13517003/ Twitter: @StrathMarine https://twitter.com/StrathMarine?lang=en-gb @strath_msrc https://twitter.com/strath_msrc Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/StrathUniNAOME FlickR: Newsletter: Magazine: Scientific journal: Other(s): ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Maritime-Safety-Research-Centre-MSRC-Dracos-Vassalos YouTube Channel: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCQUcj-LbmYH2vVP6KPBUDcQ</p>
14	UITP	<p>Website: www.uitp.org LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/uitp/ Twitter: @UITPnews</p>

Partner		Partners' website and media platforms
		Facebook: @UITPofficial FlickrR: https://www.flickr.com/photos/uitp Newsletter: UITP Direct Magazine: PTI (Public Transport International magazine) Scientific journal: Other(s): -
15	HUMANIST	Website: http://www.humanist-vce.eu LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3810190/ Twitter: @humanist_vce Facebook: N/A FlickrR: N/A Newsletter: N/A Magazine: N/A Scientific journal: N/A Other(s):
16	KT	Website: http://www.konnektable.com/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/konnektable-technologies-ltd/ Twitter: https://www.twitter.com/Konnektable [@Konnektable] Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/konnektable/ [@konnektable] FlickrR: n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): n/a
17	SCIPEDIA	Website: www.scipedia.com LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/10663823/admin/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/scipedia Facebook: n/a FlickrR: - n/a Newsletter: n/a Magazine: n/a Scientific journal: n/a Other(s): BE Open page/repository and BE Open Observatory at https://www.scipedia.com/institution/beopen-project.eu

Annex V – Key external events

Key Event	Date and Venue	Dissemination action
Annual meeting - Transport Research Board (TRB) 2019	January 13–17, 2019, Washington, D.C., USA	Presentation to the Mainstreaming International Perspectives, Networking, and Promoting International Cooperation and Collaboration Subcommittee (A0010(1))
Open Science Fair 2019	September 16-18, 2019, Porto, Portugal	Project poster presentation
European Transport Conference (ETC) 2019	October 9-11, 2019, Dublin, Ireland	First project event - Open Science in Transport Session
Annual meeting - Transport Research Board (TRB) 2020	January 12-16, 2020, Washington, D.C., USA	Project presentation
Transport research Arena (TRA2020)	April 27-30, 2020, Helsinki, Finland	Focus Session/ Second project event (tbc)
European Transport Conference (ETC) 2020	September 2020 Milan, Italy	(tbc)
Annual meeting - Transport Research Board (TRB) 2021	January (tbc), 2021, Washington, D.C., USA	Workshop

Annex VI – Partner’s and stakeholders’ events

Event	Partner(s) involved	Organiser	Date and Venue	Dissemination action
2019				
FIRM 2019	FEHRL	FEHRL	March 27-29, 2019, Brussels, Belgium	Open Science in Transport Interactive workshop
FEHRL Research Coordinators’ Meeting	FEHRL	FEHRL	April 9 – 10, 2019 Bergisch Gladbach, Germany	Project presentation
ECTRI Assembly of Members	ECTRI	ECTRI	May 7, 2019, Oslo, Norway	Open Science Session
NTUA Digitalisation and Road Safety Research Workshop	NTUA	NTUA	May 17, 2019, Athens, Greece	BE OPEN presentation
HUMANIST bi-annual Networking meeting	HUMANIST	HUMANIST	June 5, 2019, Gothenburg, Sweden	BE OPEN presentation
9th EASN International Conference	CERTH-HIT	EASN Association, Univ. of Patras and NTUA	September 3-6, 2019, Athens, Greece	BE OPEN presentation
Building EOSC through the H2020 projects	CERTH-HIT & ECTRI	EC DGs CNECT and RTD/EOSC	September 9-10, 2019, Brussels, Belgium	Engagement with EOSC and other open science related projects
Focus on Open Science: Chapter XIX Gdansk (https://www.focusopenscience.org/book/19gdansk-1/)	GUT	GUT; Scientific Knowledge Foundation	October 8, 2019 Gdansk University of Technology, Gdańsk, Poland	GUT will disseminate information about the BE OPEN
3 rd Pomeranian Open Science Conference (https://pg.edu.pl/pkos)	GUT	GUT	October 9-10, 2019	GUT will disseminate information about the BE OPEN: presentation, information poster
IATUL Seminar (https://pg.edu.pl/biblioteka-pg/iatul-seminar-redirect)	GUT	GUT, IATUL	October 9-11, 2019	GUT will disseminate information about the BE OPEN: presentation
IRTAD Meeting	VDI/VDE	ITF/IRTAD	October 22-24, 2019, Klettwitz, Germany	BE OPEN presentation
HUMANIST Network meeting	HUMANIST	HUMANIST	November 15-16, 2019, Brno, CZ	BE OPEN presentation
euroCRIS strategic membership meeting	DLR	euroCRIS	November 20, 2019, Munster,	BE OPEN presentation

Event	Partner(s) involved	Organiser	Date and Venue	Dissemination action
			Germany	
Open Science Seminar 2019 Belgian Open Science: EOSC Initiatives	ECTRI	Belgian Science Policy units	November 21, 2019, Brussels, Belgium	BE OPEN presentation
EOSC Symposium	ECTRI	DGs CNECT and RTD/EOSC	November 26-27, 2019, Budapest, Hungary	Poster
2020				
Mobilitet 2020 Conference	TØI	TØI	February 4 - 5, 2020, Oslo Norway	Stand and leaflets distribution
IT-Trans	UITP, ECTRI	UITP	March 3-5, 2019, Karlsruhe	Poster
11th International Conference „Environmental Engineering“	VG TU	VG TU	May 7–8, 2020, Vilnius, Lithuania	(tbd)
TEN-T Days 2020	FEHRL	EC/Croatian Presidency	May 13-15, 2020 Šibenik, Croatia	Promotion at FEHRL stand
AMAA 2020	VDI/VDE	VDI/VDE	May 26-27, 2020	(tbd)
HUMANIST conference	HUMANIST	HUMANIST	24 & 25 September 2020, Rhodes, Greece	(tbd)
EURNEX Assembly of Members	EURNEX	EURNEX	(tbd), 2020	(tbd)
2021				
FIRM2021	FEHRL, (others)	FEHRL	April 2021, Brussels, Belgium	(tbd)
Young Researchers Seminar	ECTRI, FEHRL	UL	June 9-11, 2021, Portorož, Slovenia	(tbd)
HUMANIST Summer School	HUMANIST	HUMANIST	July 2021	(tbd)